

Age-Based Investigation of Disruptive Interruption in TV Shows

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Abstract

People communicate effectively and continuously in daily life, and this communication process occurs between two speakers or more. Therefore, these speakers must be aware of interaction rules since it is the essential aspects of society. Usually, when someone is speaking, the listener should be listening not to break down communication rules. The listener can take a turn and start speaking when the main speaker finishes his speech and allow him/ her to speak, and this is called turn-taking. On the contrary, if the listener starts speaking before the main speaker finishes his/her speech, he/she violates the turn-taking rule. Generally, this is called the phenomenon of interruption, which takes place when the violation of turn-taking rules occurs. In other words, the listener interrupts the main speaker to take his/her turn speaking. Specifically, disruptive interruption is one of the primary purposes of interruption when the listener interrupts the speaker to show disagreement, change the topic, take the floor, or tangentialize.

The current study seeks to examine disruptive interruption according to age in live TV shows. These two factors are chosen as they are in terms of their compatibility with the current study. However, to analyze disruptive interruption according to age, this study adopts a model, uses descriptive qualitative method, and randomly selected two English-language-based live TV shows. Besides, this study selected five episodes for each TV show to get accurate results and examine disruptive interruption appropriately. Each episode was watched and listened to more than two times and then read the transcription precisely. Finally, the findings of this study indicate that, according to age, mature people use disruptive interruption more than other age classes.

Keywords: Disruptive interruption, TV live shows, turn, floor-taking, tangentialization.

1. Introduction

In a daily life conversation, interlocutors share their ideas, views, suggestions, etc., to be engaged with society. This engagement requires specific rules to be followed, such as turn-taking rules, which means that the listener should listen to the main speaker's speech and keep the rules up. If the listeners violate these rules, they apply the phenomenon of interruption. Speakers must be aware of the rules of turn-taking in order not to violate turn-taking rules. Many sociolinguists have classified the phenomenon of interruption as a clear violation of the role of the main speaker for varying purposes according to the situation of the listener. This phenomenon occurs between two or more group of interlocutors to fulfill their needs.

Concerning the phenomenon of interruption, interruption is a part of a speech act that happens when the listener violates the turn-taking rules. In other words, the listener interrupts the main speaker before completing his/her speech (Beaumont, Vasconcelos, and Ruggeri 2001:910). Moreover, Wardhaugh (2006:302) illustrates that interruption is a topic change process in an ordinary conversation. Furthermore, Zimmermann and West (1975:115) explain that the phenomenon of interruption is a concurrent speech that violates the turn-taking rules. Additionally, Zhao and Gantz (2003:349) demonstrate that it is difficult for the interruption to accomplish a smooth switch between the two speakers if the listener takes his/her turn before the main speaker finishes his/her speech.

The study investigates disruptive interruption in relation to age in live TV shows and it adopts Ptolemy's Age model (Cited in Kosior 2016:91) in this investigation. The two TV shows analyzed are "Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show" and "Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show". The reasons behind selected these two shows due to \ the age classes of the characters and the dealing with family and societal problems.

On the one hand, Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show hosted by Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana to solve the social problems related to family and betrayal. This TV show won several global and local awards. On the other hand, Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show is a TV show that attempts to make the distance between individuals close through the sympathy spirit and crucial thoughts. This TV show encourages people to have a better life and supports them to achieve their goals and get rid of their worries. However, Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show hosts different people, ages, statuses to Spread the spirit of collaboration and tranquility among people.

2. Conceptual Framework of Disruptive Interruption

Many sociolinguists explain disruptive interruption as follows: When the listener tends to compete, he takes the role of the speaker to express his opinion about the speaker's words. The listener tries to interrupt the main speaker for several purposes, such as taking the floor, changing the topic, disagreeing, or tangentializing (Yang, 2001: 2). Besides, The disruptive interruption has a detrimental influence on the speakers' relations

and the speakers themselves if it occurs (Zhao and Gantz, 2003:350). According to Murata (1994:388) and Kennedy and Camden (1983:51), Disruptive interruptions are divided into four main types: disagreement, floor-taking, topic change, and tangentialization.

2.1 Disagreement

Interruption of disagreement happens as soon as the listener disagrees with the words of the main speaker. So, the listener interrupts the main speaker to say his contrary opinion and clarify his/her point of view (Li, 2001:269). For example:

(1) **S1:** „Cause somebody tells you? Or you **figure it out**.

S2: **No. Oh.. You.**

You are talking about me, or about a deaf person.

(Tannen, 1994:43)

Example 1 shows how the listener interrupts the main speaker to show disagreement toward his/her speech.

2.2 Floor taking

Interruption of floor taking occurs when the listener interrupts the main speaker to develop the topic, then s/he takes the floor to make things wider (Murata (1994:289). For example

(2) **S1:** Um, just **to make sure.**

S2: **I have a question.**

When should I take the medication?

(Li et al. 2004:253)

Example 2 presents the role of the listener when s/he interrupts the main speaker to take the floor and develop the speech of this speaker.

2.3 Topic Change

When the listener violates the rules of turn-taking and interrupts the main speaker to change the topic, interruption of topic change occurs. (Li, 2001:269). The interrupter tries to say something different from the main topic and behaves aggressively. For example

(3) **Patient:** then I start working out and **then it's like....**

Physician: **how are your bowels**
doing lately?

(Li et al. 2004:154)

Example 3 illustrates the role of topic change and how it works. When the patient was talking about his own moments and what s/he suffers from, the doctor interrupts him/her to change the topic since s/he knows the patient's illness.

2.4 Tangentialization

Kennedy and Camden (1983:51) explain that this type of disruptive interruption occurs when the listener interrupts the main speaker in order not to hear the subject once

again. This means that the listener hears this subject before and won't hear it again. For example

(4) S1: I guess you're right, but what **I said is true too.**

S2:

I win.

So I win. I win. I win.

(Beaumont, Vasconcelos, and Ruggeri 2001:431)

Example 4 clarifies that the listener interrupts the main speaker to declare his win and prevent the repetition. The main speaker tries to put such reasons due to his/her loss. The listener won't hear the same reasons that s/he hear before.

3. Age in Conversational analysis

Regarding habits and traditions, both the father and the mother teach children to respect the speaker and never interrupt him. But the phenomenon of interruption occurs among adults for many reasons, such as proving themselves toward others. Anyhow, speakers work to preserve linguistic forms in their daily life. therefore, age, in several cultures, considered the most important factor than other factors (Labov 1994:107). In reference to identity, American adolescent speakers outperform Japanese modernizers. Besides, American adolescent speakers have a positive tendency toward their language experience more than Japanese adolescent speakers (Giles et al. 2000:34). Whereas, middle-aged speakers proceed with their language rather than lose it (Eckert cited in Coulmas, 1997:157). Moreover, middle-aged speakers have a great ethno-linguistic liveliness more than adolescent and youth speakers (Giles et al. 2000:319).

Generally, school-age children acquire different speech acts to use in different contexts (Romaine 1984:261). Additionally, in families, children and parents perform interrupt one another. Concerning families interruption, sons who interrupt others are more efficient and successful than mothers do (Mishler and Waxler cited in Beaumont, 1995:111). on the contrary, school-aged sons interrupt their mothers more than these mothers do in interaction (Beaumont 1995:116). In relation to puberty and the apex, mothers and sons use the phenomenon of interruption toward each other more than talking about themselves. When sons getting bigger, their interruption becomes higher and more influence than mothers' interruption. Whereas, fathers maintain their roles and preserve their interruption in high status since they manage everything (Steinberg 1981:839). likewise, daughters in the period of menstruation use interruption toward their fathers and brothers less than they do, but they get interrupted by their mothers frequently (Hill cited in Gunnar and Collins, 213:67).

About pausing and pacing styles, the phenomenon of interruption happens unintentionally between parents and their adolescents (Scollon cited in Goldstein, 1987:566) Contrariwise this, speakers of 21-35-year-age use their words in an ordinary conversation effectively and successfully since they use pacing and pausing styles and

conversational styles similarly. Therefore, parents' and youths' conversation is difficult due to the different use of these styles(Ibid). Even though children in society follow certain habits and rules in speaking, adults constantly interrupt each other. for instance, low-status speakers use interruption less than high-status speakers do (Henley 1973:2).

Over and above that, adolescent interlocutors use more different inserts in their interaction than adults. Whereas British youth speakers insert short words in their daily conversations (Rayson, Leech, and Hodges 1997:8). Biber et al. (2000:1093) indicate that American adolescent speakers insert polite expressions, such as "sorry" and "please", more than adults. While youth speakers use expressions like "hey" and "wow" to pay more attention. However, patterns like this found in British youth speakers' conversations(Rayson, Leech, and Hodges 1997:142). Finally, in communication, youth, high school students, and college students behave impolitely with others since they most of the time violate the rules of turn-taking (Safavi and Zamanian 2014:7).

4.Methodology

In the current study methodology, an explanation of how data are collected and analyzed will be included. Besides, the model of this study will be mention. Otherwise, there is a sufficient simplification to the method and the applied data in this study.

4.1 Model

The current study adopts Ptolemy seven stage of human life (cited in Kosior 2016:42) which is formed as follows:

Stage	Age
Early Childhood	0-4
Childhood	5-14
Adolescence	15-22
Youth	23-41
Maturity	42-56
Old age	57-68
Late old age	Over 69 years

Table (1) Ptolemy's Sseven Stage of Human Life.

Ptolemy divides age into seven stages based on ancient Rome division. He mentioned that at the age of 7, children start replacing their milk teeth and develop their speech. At the age of 7 to14, they gain the ability to do things alone. The next stage, age of 14 to 21 of human beings begin to be taller, the emergence of masculine and feminine features, and the time of the menstrual period. Otherwise, people of 21 to 28 years stop high growing. At the stage of 28 to 35 years, human beings obtain physical strength. After that, 35 to 42 years perceive this physical strength, lose it just in an accident, and behave stably. In the stage of

42 to 49 years, people start suffering from the beginning of aging, and their strength begins to get low. At the rest of the stages, people use their experiences, knowledge, and mental strength to advise others.

4.2 Data Collection

The study applies the data in conversational transcripts to select disruptive interruption applied by the participants in live TV shows. The reason behind selected live TV shows is to interpret the data realistically based on participants' live and natural reactions.

The source of the data applied to detect a disruptive interruption in live TV shows. The present study selected two live TV shows to elicit and analyze disruptive interruption. Furthermore, this study randomly selected five episodes for each TV show. The timing of these episodes is different. The two selected episodes are described below:

4.2.1 Couples Court with The Cutlers.

Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show hosted by Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana to solve the social problems related to family and betrayal. This TV show won several global and local awards. The ranged age of this TV show is between 21 and over 55. It is broadcasted since 2017.

4.2.2 Jubilee-Middle Ground

It is a live TV show that attempts to make the distance between individuals close through the sympathy spirit and crucial thoughts. This TV show encourages people to have a better life and supports them to achieve their goals and get rid of their worries. However, Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show hosts different people, ages, statuses to spread the spirit of collaboration and tranquility among people.

Many different techniques are available to use in such studies, such as document analysis, material culture, ethnography observation, meetings, interviews, and visual analysis (Vanderstoep and Johnson 2008:189). The present study applies aural and visual analysis to collect the data by watching and listening to each episode isolated and then read the transcript of each one

4.3 Procedures

Some procedures are adopted by the current study to select and analyze a disruptive interruption according to age.

- 1- Select the first, fifth, tenth, fourteenth, and sixteenth episodes for each TV show to verify the random selection.
- 2- using repetition process in watching and listening to each episode and reading the transcript.
- 3- Distinguishing Disruptive Interruption by left bracket " "

- 4- sketching a practical table to classify the data. This table contains the code of each episode, the extract, and its explanation.

4.4 Data Analysis

The process of organizing and arranging the data is done by what is called data analysis. Through this process, data are identified, and results are extracted (Moleong 2007:280). The current study used quantitative and qualitative techniques as hybrid techniques to improve the results. These techniques applied as follows:

1. Collecting and classifying the data by reading the transcript of the interaction in each episode.
2. sketching a practical table to present the collected and classified data.

Code	Dialogue	Age Class						Disruptive Interruption				Explanation
		Early Childhood	Childhood	Adolescence	Youth	Maturity	Old Age	Late Old Age	Disagreement	Floor-Taking	Topic Change	
18/S2E116/00:07:07,460 □ 00:07:19,839 Couples Court with The Cutlers.	<p>Mrs. Dana: if you thought it was gonna make him hot, you'd be like, "I got something to show you, baby. "And you'd have said, "Let me show you what I did this weekend." You'd have started with the picture...</p> <p>Mr. Keith: Instead, you know...</p> <p>Mrs. Dana: You are like</p> <p>... Fine</p>				✓				✓			<p>Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana present a special episode about betrayal. They host Samsonoff (38 years), the wife, and Monero (41 years), the husband, to talk about Monero's accusation of his girlfriend Samsonoff. Monero tells the judges that Samsonoff is betraying him with her friend Amanda. In this extraction, When Samsonoff tells Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana that she is betraying Monero with her friend Amanda, Mrs. Dana clarifies that Samsonoff tries to dislodge Monero and do more than betrayal just because she is jealous of him. Mr. Keith attempts to interrupt Mrs. Dana disruptively to take the</p>

3. Excerpting the occurrence frequency of disruptive interruption according to age in the selected TV shows.

4. Using the attached equation to extract the percentage:

$$P = \frac{x}{y} \times 100$$

P = Percentages. **X** = Total number of disruptive interruption.

Y = Total collected data

5. Extracting the conclusions of the current study depends on the results.

5. Findings

The current study presents the occurrence frequency and percentage of disruptive interruption according to age performed by the participants in the selected TV shows. In reference to age, the results show that there are 65 of the data collected from the selected live TV shows related to disruptive interruption. The total frequency, as well as the percentage of the data, are shown in the table below:

Live TV Shows	Age	Disruptive Interruption				Total %
		Disagreement	Floor-Taking	Topic Change	Tangentialization	
Couples Court with The Cutlers	41	10	22	8	1	41
						63.05%
<i>Jubilee – Middle Ground</i>	24	6	9	6	3	24
						36.95%
Total %	65	16	31	14	4	65
	100%	24.61%	47.70%	21.54%	6.15%	100%

Table (3) The Total Frequency of Occurrences of Disruptive Interruption According to Age.

Table (3) demonstrates that four subtypes of disruptive interruption happen in ten episodes of the selected live TV shows, i.e., disagreement, floor-taking, topic change, and tangentialization, and this agrees with (Ferguson 1977), who mentions that the four subtypes of disruptive interruption occurred in a conversation and among participants.

The above statistics mention that disruptive interruption performed by the participants 65 times, distributed as follows: First, floor-taking used by the participants 31 times represents (47.70%). Disagreement interruption came secondly and applied 16 times, representing (24.61%). In the third place, topic change used 14 times which forms (14%). Finally, tangentialization performed only four times, representing (6.15%). The percentage of the four subtypes of disruptive interruption is presented in figure (1).

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Figure (1) Frequency Percentage of Disruptive Interruption at Ten Episodes.

In the light of TV shows, the participants of Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show applied disruptive interruption 40 times, representing (63.05%). Whereas the Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show participants performed disruptive interruption 24 times, which forms (36.95%). The percentage of the two TV shows are presented in figure (2).

Figure (2) Frequency Percentage of Disruptive Interruption in Live TV shows.

Finally, according to age, a disruptive interruption occurred as follows: Firstly, old age speakers perform disruptive interruption in the selected live TV shows 29 times, representing (44.61%). Secondly, mature speakers use disruptive interruption 25 times, which forms (38.46%). Thirdly, Adolescents apply disruptive interruption six times, representing (9.23%). Lastly, youth speakers perform disruptive interruption five times.

Which forms (7.7%). the total percentage is shown in figure (3).

Figure (3) The total Percentage of Disruptive Interruption According to Age Groups.

6. Discussions

In discussion, many interpretation and justifications about disruptive interruption and interruption interface, age, are presented.

6.1 Age

Age is the time a person lives from birth to death. Many age groups distinguish a person from one person to another—for example, babies, children, teens, young adults, and the elderly. The current study adopts Ptolemy seven stage of human life (cited in Kosior 2016:42), as mentioned in (4.1 Model).

In the analysis process, only four age groups are found. The selected TV programs did not include the age groups from 4 years old to 15 years old. The age groups included in the analysis process are adolescents, youth, mature, and old age speakers.

In the light of Age, disruptive interruption performed 64 times by the participants of Couples Court with the Cutlers and Jubilee-Middle Ground TV shows. Table 4 shows how many times disruptive interruption are applied according to age groups. Old age speakers use disruptive interruption 29 times in their interaction. Moreover, mature speakers applied disruptive interruption 25 times.

Besides, adolescents speakers performed interruption disruptively six times. Finally, Youth speakers used disruptive interruption only five times. These results disagree with what Adeeb and Abbas (2019) found. They mentioned that teenagers interrupt others more than adults do. See table (4).

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Age Groups	Disruptive Interruption				Total %
	Disagreement	Floor-Taking	Topic Change	Tangentialization	
15-22 (Adolescence)	4	1	1	0	6
23-41 (Youth)	2	2	1	0	5
42-56 (Maturity)	6	9	8	2	25
57-68 (Old Age)	8	12	7	2	29
Total %	16	29	16	4	65
	24.62 %	44.61 %	24.62 %	6.15%	100%

Table (4) Frequency of Occurrence of Interruption Types and Purposes According to Age.

In reference to subtypes of disruptive interruption, Old age and mature speakers use floor-taking purpose more than adolescents and youth to interrupt others. Old age speakers use floor taking 12 times, and mature speakers perform it nine times. These findings disagree with Putri's findings (2014), but they agree with Amalia's findings (2016). The reasons behind using floor-taking purpose by these two groups more than others are age difference from other groups, experience, prestige, tendencies to prove oneself. Consider the following extract:

Data 9

Ms. Phoenix: I have suspicions that my boyfriend is **cheating still**.

Mr. Keith: Still?

(9/S3E9/00:00:25,858 - -> 00:00:30,096)

In this episode, Mr Keith and Mrs Dana host Ricks and Phoenix in Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show to review their problem about Phoenix's suspicions of her boyfriend Ricks's cheating with a close friend.

In this extract, Phoenix is expressing her suspicion that her boyfriend is still cheating on her. Mr Keith carries out a disruptive interruption to take the floor to ask her astonishingly since Keith take Phoenix's words as a sign of lack of experience although she is an older woman and Phoenix got the necessary life experiences.

6.2 Disruptive Interruption

Disruptive interruption occurs when the listener wants to show disagreement, change the topic, take the floor, or tangentialize.

6.2.1 Disagreement

Disagreement interruption takes place in a conversation when the listener interrupts the speaker's speech to give a different opinion and show disagreement toward this speech. Old age speakers apply this type of disruptive interruption more than other age groups. Consider the following extract.

Data 50

Jeremiah: Yeah, I mean the question was "Do you think that teen is innocent?"

But when I say teen's...

Elizabeth:

But I still think It's 50/50 you'll stand your friends.

(50/S4E3/00:03:21,445 □ 00:03:29,389)

This TV show presents different and unique topics about social life. Many different people and ages participate in this TV show to talk about certain related subjects. Mateo, 16-year-old, Taylor, 18-year-old, Isabella, 16 years old, Fanny, 39-year-old Elizabeth, 36-year-old, and Jeremiah, 41-year-old, participate in this episode. In this extract, Jeremiah talks about teens and their lives. Suppose they are innocent or not. Jeremiah suspects that teenagers are not innocent and that their actions are not balanced. Then Elizabeth interrupts him to show disagreement toward what he said.

6.2.2 Floor-Taking

Floor taking interruption happens when the listener interrupts the main speaker before finishing his/her speech to clarify something. This purpose sometimes is successful and sometimes is unsuccessful. In another word, the listener may take the floor from the speaker if the last one does not insist on his turn to continue.

Data 18

Mrs. Dana: if you thought it was gonna make him hot, you'd be like, "I got something to show you, baby. "And you'd have said, "Let me show

you what I did this weekend." You'd have started **with the picture...**

Mr. Keith:

Instead, you know...

Mrs. Dana:

You are like ... Fine.

(18/S2E116/ 00:07:07,460 □ 00:07:19,839)

Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana present a special episode about betrayal. They host Samsonoff (38 years), the wife, and Monero (41 years), the husband, to talk about Monero's accusation of his girlfriend Samsonoff. Monero tells the judges that Samsonoff is betraying him with her friend Amanda. In this extraction, When Samsonoff tells Mr. Keith and Mrs. Dana that she is betraying Monero with her friend Amanda, Mrs. Dana clarifies that Samsonoff tries to dislodge Monero and do more than betrayal just because she is jealous of him. Mr. Keith attempts to interrupt Mrs. Dana disruptively to take the floor and share what he thinks about that, but he failed. Mrs. Dana maintained her turn talking and finished what she wants to say.

6.2.3 Topic Change

Topic change interruption takes place when the listener does not want to keep talking about this subject or does not want to answer such a question. The interruption directs a different question, phrase, order, or word to change the main speaker's topic. Mature speakers use this kind of purposes to show their tendencies about that topics. For example:

Data 32

Mrs. Dana: Okay, Ms. Willette, we've got the failing to text, you got him as "Mr. Friendlier the neighborhood",

What else do you have?

John:

And do you got proof?

(32/S1E37/00:03:37,449 □ 00:03:45,458)

In this episode, Mr Keith and Mrs Dana host Willette and John to talk about her suspicions about john's betrayal of her. Mrs Dana sought to clarify the points Mrs Willett make about her suspicion of John's infidelity and asks her if there are other things she would like to say. John at this point interrupts Mrs Dana to change the topic and asks Mrs Dana if they found evidence of her claims. John successes in taking the floor from Willette by asking Mrs Dana a different question.

6.2.4 Tangentialization

This type of disruptive interruption occurs when the listener wants not to hear the

topic again, or when s/he wants to give a summary of the speaker's speech or add something valuable to the speaker's speech. Consider the following example.

Data 1

Mr. Keith: So, Mr. Ricks, you weren't married to the woman, but you were having a sexual relationship with her?

Mr. Ricks: Uff...

Ms. Phoenix: Oh, just yes or no?

Mr. Ricks: Your Honor, we was...Like I said, we was broken up for two weeks. (47/S3E9/00:14:14,619□00:14:05,577)

In this extract, Mr Keith asks him to see if he loved Mrs Phoenix or just considered her a body that Ricks fulfilled his needs through. Again Mr Ricks starts stuttering and does not know what to say. So, Ms Phoenix interrupts him directly to get an answer to the question. Mrs Phoenix wants not to hear his justifications once again.

7. Conclusions

The conclusions of the current study are as follows:

1. Old age speakers interrupt other speakers disruptively more than other age groups.
2. Mature speakers use topic change purpose in their interactions more than other age groups.
3. Old age speakers use tangentialization purpose similarly to mature speakers in their interactions.
4. The most use of disruptive purposes by the participants is floor-taking purpose.
5. Participants of Couples Court with the Cutlers TV show use disruptive interruption more than Jubilee-Middle Ground TV show.

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